

Aeroacoustics of coaxial co-rotating propellers: experimental analysis and mid-fidelity prediction

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This work investigates the advantages and limitations of fast turnaround methods for the prediction of the aerodynamic performance and tonal noise emissions of coaxial co-rotating propellers. An extensive aeroacoustic experimental campaign has been performed to confirm the trends highlighted in previous literature, further investigate the relation between propulsive efficiency and noise emissions, and provide a database for the validation of the numerical methodology. A surface panel method is used to predict the aerodynamic coefficients. The pressure distribution on the blade surface is used to predict the tonal noise using a rotating dipole formulation. This combination of numerical tools successfully predicts the trends observed experimentally and can thus be used in optimization studies involving phase offset angle and axial separation distance, allowing a fully virtual preliminary design of co-rotating propellers.

I. Introduction

Urban Air Mobility marks a revolutionary shift in transportation, and with the rapid advancements in eVTOL technology, there's a growing focus on overcoming aerodynamic and aeroacoustic challenges. The study of coaxial co-rotating propeller systems focuses on optimizing aerodynamic and acoustic performance for varying axial distances and phase offset angles. Experimental, theoretical, and computational tools are used to explore the trade-offs between noise and propulsion, with special attention to vortex and wake interactions.

Previous works revealed that axial proximity increases lift on the leading blade and decreases it on the trailing blade due to potential interaction effects [1]. These effects can be estimated with Kutta-Joukowski and Biot-Savart laws. At the same time, azimuthal spacing was shown to offer significant rotor thrust control [1, 2]. High-speed flow diagnostics identified vortex behaviors, with optimal index angles allowing upper rotor vortices to interact beneficially with the lower rotor, enhancing performance and minimizing the noise emissions [2].

On the modeling side, high-fidelity CFD was successfully employed to simulate the aerodynamic coefficients of such systems [3]. On the contrary, mid-fidelity solvers like panel methods and vortex particle methods have limited accuracy due to the inviscid assumption and simplifications in the modeling of the induced velocity [1, 4]. To the best of the authors' knowledge, the use of fast turnaround methods for the acoustic prediction has never been attempted for such systems.

This work focuses on conducting a numerical and experimental analysis of rotor-rotor potential and viscous interferences in coaxial co-rotating propellers in hovering conditions. The primary objective is to experimentally explore the trade-off between performance and noise footprint for varying phase offset angle and axial distance. Another key goal is to use the experimental results to validate a combination of fast-turnaround numerical tools, evaluating the advantages and limitations of a fully virtual design approach for these propulsive systems. The numerical methodology employs a surface vorticity panel method to predict the aerodynamic performance. The pressure distribution on the blade surface is used to predict the tonal noise emissions by using the formulation of the noise emitted by a rotating dipole.

II. Methodology

A. Measurements

The experimental investigations on performance and acoustics have been carried out in the ALCOVES facility of the von Karman Institute for Fluid Dynamics (VKI). This anechoic chamber hosts aeroacoustic tests on drone-sized propellers with a dedicated dual-axis instrumented shaft, capable of measuring the aerodynamics of coaxial co-rotating and contra-rotating propellers, and a sliding 24-microphone antenna to depict the soundscape around them. More details

Fig. 1 Disposition of microphones on the antenna.

regarding the commissioning of the facility can be found in references [5, 6]. The type of propeller adopted in the study is a Mejzlik 13" x 4,2 P carbon fiber propeller of 30 cm diameter.

1. Performance Measurements

In ALCOVES, the thrust and aerodynamic torque have been measured for a total of 116 configurations of coaxial co-rotating propellers, at a fixed rotational speed of 6000 RPM, for different axial distances z and phase offset angles ϕ between the propellers. The axial distance ranges between 21 mm and 42 mm with a 7 mm increment, corresponding to normalized values of $\Delta z/R = 0.13$, $\Delta z/R = 0.17$, $\Delta z/R = 0.21$, and $\Delta z/R = 0.25$, respectively. The phase offset ranges from -90° to 90° with an angle step of 10° at the extremities of the phase angle domain, increased to 5° between -50° and 50° , where the influence of ϕ is expected to have a stronger impact on performance. The measured data have been processed to obtain dimensionless coefficients for thrust and power, C_T and C_P , and the power loading, PL. The latter is a figure of merit for efficiency, which has been exploited as a link between performance and acoustics. They are defined as

$$C_T = \frac{F_T}{\rho n^2 D^4}, \quad C_P = \frac{P}{\rho n^3 D^5}, \quad PL = \frac{T}{Q\Omega},$$

with F_T the thrust, $P = 2\pi n Q$ the absorbed power, Q the torque, ρ the air density, Ω the rotational speed in radians per second, $n = \text{RPM}/60$, and D the propeller's diameter. The torque is measured by a Futek QTA141 (QSH01827) sensor attached to the static part of the motor; the thrust is measured by a Futek LCM100 (FSH03828) load cell.

The rotational speed of the shaft is measured by a Vishay TCRT5000 tachometer, which consists of an infrared-emitting diode and a phototransistor detector. The shaft is driven by a T-Motor AT2814 Long Shaft brushless motor, typical of small UAV applications. The RPM is controlled with a Tribunus II 12-80A ESC SBEC controller.

2. Noise Measurements

The 24 G.R.A.S. type 40PL microphones were set up in three horizontal arrays of 8, mounted on a motorized system that spanned from -0.4 m to 0.4 m relative to the propeller axis. The top view of the antenna is shown in fig. 1. Calibration was done using a pistonphone type 4231 B&K, producing a 1 kHz tone at 94 dB.

Noise emissions were recorded for 62 configurations from the performance test matrix, focusing on different power loading values. The aim was to provide a point-wise comparison of the noise emitted at minimum and maximum propulsive efficiency, and compare the noise of $(\phi, \Delta z/R)$ configurations delivering the same thrust at different efficiency

Fig. 2 Tesselation of co-rotating propellers. The red line indicates the trailing edge of the blades.

levels. For the axial distances of $\Delta z/R = 0.17$ and $\Delta z/R = 0.21$, acoustic measurements were taken with a fine phase offset resolution to establish a continuous relationship between noise and efficiency with ϕ .

For data acquisition, a cDAQ-9178 chassis with six NI-9234 modules allowed simultaneous recording of 24 channels at 51.2 kHz for 30 seconds. The signals were bandpass-filtered between 10 Hz and 20 kHz using a 5th-order Butterworth filter. Tonal noise levels were evaluated by integrating the power spectral density at blade passing frequencies, while the broadband noise (BBN) was isolated using a moving median filter with a 300 Hz window size. Overall broadband noise levels (OABBN) were computed by integrating the spectrum from 600 Hz to 12 kHz.

B. Numerical Simulations

A combined use of numerical tools for aeroacoustics prediction has been tested on a subset of the test domain, aiming to allow a fast and robust simulation of the aerodynamic loads and noise soundscape around the propellers. The commercial software FlightStream, based on an enhanced vortex panel method, has been employed to simulate the pressure field distribution on the propellers' blades. The surface pressure has been directly fed into VKI's in-house software BATMAN[™] to predict tonal noise levels.

1. Aerodynamic Simulations

FlightStream is a commercial software for aerodynamics simulations based on a surface vorticity method enhanced with a Prandtl-Glauert correction for compressibility effects. It features a viscous correction to couple the potential flow solution with a numerical boundary layer, assumed a priori by the user and provided as input. A convergence study was carried out on a single propeller simulation at 6000 RPM. The simulation parameters were then adjusted to the co-rotating propeller set-up to preserve the stability of the simulation. In particular, the simulations for the co-rotating cases lasted 8 full revolutions with a time increment of 0.3 ms, corresponding to approximately 10° . The wake was interrupted after 1.5 propeller diameters to reduce the computational cost. Each blade was discretized with about 2550 triangles, with a size of 2.1 mm on the blade tip, leading and trailing edges, and 4.2 mm in the central part. Figure 2 shows the surface mesh adopted.

Fig. 3 Performance measurements for axial distance $\Delta z/R = 0.21$.

2. Acoustic Simulations

BATMAN^π (Broadband And Tonal Models for Airfoil Noise) in-house software is employed to predict the tonal noise emissions. It uses Goldstein's formulation [7] for the noise emitted by a rotating dipole. The blades are divided into 14 acoustically compact patches. Each patch models a moving dipolar source with thrust F_T and drag F_D obtained from the integration of the surface pressure simulated by FlightStream. For each patch, the acoustic pressure at the n -th blade passing frequency for a listener at coordinates (x, θ, φ) is computed as

$$p_{nB} = \frac{iBk_{nB}}{4\pi x} e^{-ik_{nB}x} \sum_{p=-\infty}^{\infty} e^{-i(nB-p)(\varphi-\pi/2)} \left[-J_{-nB+p}(-k_{nB}r' \sin \theta) F_p^{(T)} \cos \theta + \frac{nB-p}{k_{nB}r'} J_{-nB+p}(-k_{nB}r' \sin \theta) F_p^{(D)} \right], \quad (1)$$

where B is the number of blades, $k_{nB} = nB\Omega/c_0$, c_0 the speed of sound, J_m is the Bessel function of first kind and order m , $F_p^{(T)}$ and $F_p^{(D)}$ are the Fourier coefficients of order p of the thrust and drag forces.

III. Results

A. Aerodynamic Results

Figure 3 presents measured performance for the axial separation $\Delta z/R = 0.21$. A sinusoidal pattern for C_T is noticed, with a maximum for $\phi \approx -30^\circ$ and a minimum for $\phi \approx 30^\circ$. Similar values were found for the other axial distances tested, suggesting that the phase offset plays a more important role in the performance compared to axial spacing. The measured torque appeared noisier, but an oscillating pattern was still visible with a minimum for $\phi \approx 0^\circ$. The power loading showed a saw-tooth pattern, with a maximum found for a slightly negative clocking angle. As the configuration approached orthogonal propellers, the power loading stabilized to a constant value. The lowest efficiency was measured between $\phi = 10^\circ$ and $\phi = 60^\circ$.

Figure 4 summarizes the aerodynamic measurements for all the axial distances investigated. Thrust maxima were obtained for negative phase offset angles (i.e., the lower-leading configurations, when the downstream propeller is encountering the undisturbed flow first), while the highest power loading were achieved for zero (parallel propellers) or slightly negative phase offset, where the potential interaction is stronger. Similar findings were found in [1]. In contrast, the aerodynamic performance for the upper-leading configurations appeared to be degraded, probably because of the impingement of the wake shed by the upper propeller onto the lower one. Generally, both the viscous and potential

Fig. 4 Measured aerodynamic performances within test domain.

Fig. 5 Simulated power loading within test domain.

interactions between the propellers, modulated by both degrees of freedom, dictate the sinusoidal behavior of the aerodynamic coefficients.

Figure 5 shows the power loading computed with FlightStream within the test domain. Even though the transition between high and low power loadings for low offset angles is qualitatively retrieved, the absolute values are overpredicted by the numerical tool, as shown in fig. 6 for $\Delta z/R = 0.13$. Furthermore, the numerical simulations show a degraded accuracy for the upper-leading configurations, likely because the wake-blade interactions are dominant in that region.

B. Aeroacoustics Results

Figure 7 shows the measured OABBN, the tonal noise levels, and the power loading for $-60^\circ < \phi < +60^\circ$ and $\Delta z/R = 0.17$. Curves qualitatively similar for $\Delta z/R = 0.21$ are obtained. Higher levels of OABBN are measured for the upper-leading configurations, confirming the blade-wake interaction for these configurations, as noticed by Akif et al.

Fig. 6 Comparison between measured and simulated power loading for $\Delta z/R = 0.13$.

Fig. 7 Overall aeroacoustics results for $\Delta z/R = 0.17$ mm and $-60^\circ < \phi < +60^\circ$. Frontal position (M11), at $y = 100$ mm with respect to the propeller plane.

Fig. 8 Noise directivity measurements for axial distance $\Delta z/R = 0.17$.

[8]. On the other hand, the power loading and the tonal noise at 200 Hz seem to correlate well, with both reaching their maximum for slightly negative offset angles.

Noise emissions have been further analyzed by comparing the two pairs of configurations reported in fig. 3. The first pair of points corresponds to maximum and minimum power loading configurations, namely ‘Max PL’ and ‘Min PL’, while the second pair corresponds to the points with approximately the same thrust, ‘T₁’ and ‘T₂’, which are denoted as ‘PL1’ and ‘PL2’ in fig. 3. Starting by comparing the noise emissions of ‘Max PL’ and ‘Min PL’ configurations, tonal noise levels at 200 Hz show negligible differences, except for the upstream positions, where the higher noise levels are measured for the maximum power loading. In contrast, the OABBN levels are consistently higher for the minimum power loading configuration, as the blade-wake interaction is likely responsible for both the increase in OABBN and the degradation of performance. The same trends have been observed for all the separation distances investigated.

Figure 9 shows the noise directivity for two conditions with the same thrust, namely ‘PL1’ and ‘PL2’ in fig. 3. In this case, the OABBN is unchanged between the two configurations, while the tonal noise is significantly higher for the configuration with a lower phase offset angle. For both configurations, the effect of blade-wake interactions is minimal, yielding similar levels of OABBN. However, constructive acoustic interference between the two rotors is likely responsible for the increase in tonal noise.

BATMAN^π successfully captured the same trends in tonal noise observed in the experimental analyses, both when comparing minimum and maximum efficiency configurations and when examining fixed thrust configurations. Figure 10 and fig. 11 show the numerical results for $\Delta z/R = 0.17$. In particular, we can observe from fig. 10 that BATMAN^π predicted the same tonal noise at minimum and maximum power loads, as observed experimentally. Similarly, numerical predictions at constant thrust recover the increase in tonal noise at observed in the measurements (fig. 11). The average discrepancy of +15% from the measured levels of tonal noise at first BPF is attributed to a similar amount of load

Fig. 9 Noise directivity measurements for axial distance $\Delta z/R = 0.17$.

Fig. 10 Comparison of tonal noise at the second harmonic, minimum and maximum power loading comparison, $\Delta z/R = 0.17$, at $y = 100$ mm with respect to propeller plane.

overestimation in FlightStream simulations, while the mismatch in the directivity shape might be attributed to installation effects and recirculation in the test chamber.

IV. Conclusions

The measurements confirmed that the phase offset ϕ affects performance more than the axial distance z . Furthermore, increasing the axial distance weakens this effect. Offset angles ϕ between 0° and -40° maximize the power loading and minimize the broadband noise emissions. In contrast, the tonal noise at the first BPF increases significantly for small offset angles.

FlightStream succeeded in retrieving the trends of thrust and torque of the co-rotating propeller system in the configurations without blade-wake (i.e., viscous) interaction. However, the blade-wake interaction is associated with a degradation of the aerodynamic and acoustic performances of the system, and hence, it is less interesting for an optimization of the system. For this reason, panel methods like FlightStream can still be considered in optimization studies. BATMAN^π qualitatively captured the trends in tonal noise observed in the measurements and can thus be coupled with panel methods for a preliminary aeroacoustic characterization of coaxial co-rotating propellers.

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Fig. 11 Comparison of tonal noise at second harmonic, fixed thrust analysis, $\Delta z/R = 0.17$, at $y = 100$ mm with respect to propeller plane.

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